

The soil at the site had pH 10.3, 0.08% organic carbon, 1.25% calcium carbonate, 80.4% exchangeable sodium, and 0.52 ppm available Zn. The treatments are in the table.

Before the experiment, 50% of the gypsum requirement was mixed in the 15 cm soil layer of all the plots. Thirty-day-old PR106 rice seedlings were transplanted to submerged soils in all plots and fertilized with 120 kg N/ha as urea and 26 kg P/ha as superphosphate.

Rice plants grew poorly in control plots and exhibited typical Zn deficiency symptoms. Zinc application, irrespective of method, caused significant increase in grain yield and increased Zn content of 40-day-old leaves, straw, and grain (see table). Soil application of ZnSO₄ before transplanting produced maximum grain yield (140% over control). Topdressing ZnSO₄ 7 or 15 days after transplanting produced similar grain yield. Foliar spray of 1% or 2% ZnSO₄ solution increased

Effect of methods of zinc application on zinc content and rice grain yield.^a

Treatment	Grain yield ^b (t/ha)	Increase (%) Over control	Zinc content (ppm)		
			Leaf ^c	Straw	Grain
Root dip					
2% ZnO suspension	3.2	74	15.1	16.3	9.9
4% ZnO suspension	3.3	81	15.7	17.1	10.4
Foliar sprays (3)					
1% ZnSO ₄ solution	2.5	38	16.2	14.2	9.4
2% ZnSO ₄ solution	2.8	55	16.7	15.1	9.7
Root dip + foliar sprays (2)					
2% ZnO suspension + 1% ZnSO ₄	3.9	115	18.6	17.6	10.6
4% ZnO suspension + 1% ZnSO ₄	4.1	126	19.8	18.4	11.0
Soil application of 50 kg ZnSO ₄ /ha					
Before transplanting	4.3	140	17.6	18.8	12.2
7 days after transplanting	4.2	133	17.1	19.3	11.9
15 days after transplanting	4.0	123	16.2	18.5	11.2
Control	1.8	—	10.8	11.7	8.9
CD at 5%	0.4	—	0.9	0.9	1.0

^aAv of 3 replications. ^bOven-dry basis. ^cForty-day-old.

yield significantly over the control, but was inferior to all other methods of zinc application. Dipping rice seedling roots in

a 4% ZnO suspension supplemented with foliar sprays of 1% ZnSO₄ solution gave yields similar to ZnSO₄ application. □

Environment and its influence

Low water temperature and sterility in rice

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Rice plants are most sensitive to low temperature during meiosis or when the auricle distance between the flag leaf and the leaf immediately below is zero. Low temperature at this stage usually causes high spikelet sterility. In some rice growing areas, fields are flooded above the growing point of plants to protect them from cold air temperature at night. Irrigation water is warmer than ambient air and protects the growing point from cold night air.

In some rice growing areas, however, irrigation water is cooler than the air temperature. Tests in Chuncheon, Korea, showed that 17°C water temperature can cause 100% sterility (see figure). However, water depth and plant height or position of the growing point during

Sterility of rice cultivars treated with low water temperature at different stages of panicle development.

meiosis were important factors. Tall plants, like Leng Kwang, escaped cold water injury because panicle height from soil surface was greater. Seulak

(Cheoulwon 21), a short variety, was seriously damaged, even in shallow water. In Chuncheon, where the water is colder than air, shallow water is preferable.

Results also showed that plants are most sensitive to low temperature when auricle distance is -15 or -10 cm. □

Announcements

Seed Technology Course

The University of Edinburgh is offering a 1-year graduate course leading to a diploma or MSc in seed technology. The course is intended to train personnel for senior technical and managerial posts in

seed industries, particularly in developing countries.

It covers all aspects of seed technology including production, processing, storage, marketing, quality control, legislation and management with emphasis on major cereal crops. Special attention is given to

the organization and development of national seed programs.

For further information write: The Course Director, Seed Technology, the Edinburgh School of Agriculture, West Mains Road, Edinburgh, EH 9 3JG, Scotland, UK. □

Khan named Fellow

Dr. Amir U. Khan, Agricultural Engineering Department, IRRI, has been named a Fellow of the Pakistan Society of Agricultural Engineers in recognition of his contribution to agricultural engineering in Pakistan and of his work with the variety.

New IRRI publications

New IRRI publications available for purchase from the Information Services Department, Division C, IRRI, P.O. Box 933, Manila, Philippines are:

Agroclimatic and dry-season maps of South, Southeast, and East Asia

Biology and management of riceland rats in Southeast Asia

Field problems of tropical rice (rev. ed.)

Parentage of IRRI crosses IR1-IR30,000

Rice area by type of culture: South, Southeast Asia and East Asia

Technical handbook for the paddy rice postharvest technology

Brown planthopper publications

Two reports discussing brown planthopper (BPH) *Nilaparvata lugens* are available from the Centre for Overseas Pest Research, College House, Wrights Lane, London W85SJ, UK.

Miscellaneous Report No. 57 - A pos-

sible correlation between light trap catches of BPH and the stage of development of the rice crop, 22 p., £9.40 - concludes that periods of rice harvest can be used to predict the presence of macropterous emigrants in areas where no BPH surveys occur.

Miscellaneous Report No. 58 - Bibliography and geographical index of literature on BPH, 163 p., £10.50 - compiled in 1979, identifies country and locality where research was conducted, the nature of the work, and the source of BPH used in laboratory experiments. □